

THE VOCABULARY IS THE BASIS OF THE LANGUAGE.

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Annotation

This article discusses the importance of vocabulary in the culture of communication and the fact that vocabulary is the foundation of language.

Key words

Educational technologies, vocabulary, culture of communication, grammar, foreign languages, innovation.

Аннотация

В этой статье обсуждается важность словарного запаса в культуре общения и тот факт, что словарный запас является основой языка.

Ключевые слова

Образовательные технологии, лексика, культура общения, грамматика, иностранные языки, инновации.

Annotatsiya

ushbu maqolada lug'atning muloqot madaniyatidagi ahamiyati va lug'at tilning asosi ekanligi muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar

ta'lim texnologiyalari, lug'at, muloqot madaniyati, grammatika, chet tillari, innovatsiya.

INTRODUCTION

In the current era of rapid development, science and technology are also developing rapidly. Successes are achieved in all sectors. Especially in science there are big changes and important results. Every science is new. Providing students with the use of innovative educational technologies is one of the most important needs of today's education. Finally, our Head of State Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: “For the future of foreign language education in our country, it is time to build a new system with a solid foundation. The goal is to build a competitive country, because school, high school, university and high school graduates must know at least 2 foreign languages and master them perfectly. This is a strict requirement for the head of any educational institution and should

become the main criterion for activity." also learn their habits. Nations help, create unlimited possibilities for communication and communication in different directions. In our country, the world scientific achievements of the young generation are supported by the wide use of technologies and the conditions created for teaching and learning languages abroad. Highly qualified staff is getting better every year. Nowadays, the importance of learning and mastering foreign languages is increasing. To become a mature expert in any field, the world is beyond one's native language. It is necessary to know at least two or three languages. Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirmonovich Mirziyoyev: It is time to introduce a new system of teaching foreign languages, which will be a solid foundation for the future. On May 6, chaired by President Shavkat Mirmonovich Mirziyoyev, a video selection session dedicated to measures to improve the foreign language education system was held. It is time to introduce a new system of teaching foreign languages, which will be a solid foundation for the future of our country. As we aim to build a competitive country, graduates of schools, high schools, colleges and universities must master at least 2 foreign languages immediately. This strict requirement should become the main criterion for the activity of the head of an educational institution, - said Shavkat Mirmonovich Mirziyoyev.

When it comes to learning a foreign language like English, many people don't realize that working on vocabulary is just as important, if not more important, to being successful in learning a foreign language. The question arises in our mind, what is the role of the horse? Wording is indeed very important in expressing our thoughts effectively. Vocabulary means words. To learn any language, we need to know grammar and vocabulary perfectly. Vocabulary is the most important skill in teaching a foreign language. All other skills such as reading, writing, speaking and listening are built and developed from vocabulary. This showed why learning new words is important. Vocabulary helps students express themselves more clearly and improves communication skills, and also requires students to have cognitive academic language skills. When students master more than 90-95% of the vocabulary words, it helps students understand what other people are saying and what they are reading. Without adequate understanding of words, students have difficulty understanding others or expressing themselves. Vocabulary instruction is important across the curriculum, from language arts and social studies to math and science. Certain techniques can help the teacher help students pronounce a specific word. In order to have a rich vocabulary, students must not only learn as many words as possible, but also memorize them, because learning is remembering. In

this regard, several methods have been developed to help students memorize words effectively, and teachers can facilitate the learning process for their students. One of the methods a teacher can use to teach vocabulary is repetition. This is an important technique in teaching vocabulary. Another important technique is the use of newly learned words. The role of teachers is also precious in this sense. In the classroom, teachers should encourage students to talk as much as possible and require vocabulary practice by designing vocabulary-based activities and games. closely related to Another technique to consider in both learning and teaching vocabulary is imagination. Students learn new words easily when they are taught to associate them with their pictures. For example, if the topic is about a travel agency and students have learned to visualize and show a picture of a building that we show them for travel information, they will remember the word for a long time. possible Then the students have to imagine the words they have to learn. It aids the learning process and holds the word in long-term memory. Vocabulary is important when learning a new language. Because it can be defined by words of language. Includes phrases or multi-word fragments that have a specific meaning as separate words. Learning a language has many aspects. Especially for English learners, but English vocabulary is most important. Basically, vocabulary is a very important part of communication. Because it improves all areas of communication and without it we cannot express our feelings. For example, a solid English vocabulary improves overall communication; listen, speak, read and write. A large number of words will help you express your thoughts in a meaningful way. Vocabulary is the key to learning English. Expand your vocabulary by choosing the right words. So you can understand quickly without wasting much time. Follow these steps to quickly memorize vocabulary.

* Learn by writing. First, write the words in a notebook. This is the most effective way to enhance vocabulary studies to learn the most common words. Regular writing practice is the key to maintaining vocabulary. Vocabulary is an important part of English communication. This is essential for any prospect, whether it's writing a resume, reading a book, or understanding people's opinions. Vocabulary also makes essay writing more engaging and understandable.

* Learn by listening. If you come across interesting words in your daily conversation, try to use them in context. By experimenting and practicing the art of speech, you can use the word correctly in a given context.

* Learn vocabulary by reading. Basically, you can learn words by reading books and magazines. The context of the word is enough to guess the meaning. Using words often in reading teaches you how to use these sentences in speaking

and writing. Also, read both fiction and non-fiction for best results. This is a great way to learn new words in English. Learn about the words you read: Vocabulary can be divided into two parts - Active Vocabulary and Passive Vocabulary. Active Vocabulary is a collection of all the words that you can easily understand or use yourself. Follow these steps to learn English easily:

- * Repeat the words many times.
- * Put words into separate groups.
- * Imagine images and convert them into words.
- * Test yourself using words in speaking or writing exercises.
- * Write hard-to-use words and definitions.

Vocabulary is important because it is the foundation of all languages. It is the raw material that we can use to express our thoughts and ideas, share information, understand others and build personal relationships. Even if we barely speak the language and don't understand the grammar, we can still make ourselves understood. As British linguist David A. Wilkins poignantly points out, "very little can be communicated without grammar; nothing can be transmitted without a vocabulary. If you're still not completely convinced, think about how children acquire language. They say simple words like "duck", "ball" and "plush" before trying to do more complex constructions, and can usually say what they want. However, as with ESL students, their ability to communicate becomes more effective as their language skills develop. But the point here is that they still can only communicate with the help of vocabulary. In general, English vocabulary has three aspects. This is due to the use of layers of meaning related to the form, meaning and roots of individual words. Vocabulary learning is not limited to words. This involves knowledge of literal expressions and English vocabulary. It is the most important skill for learning a language.

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